

(CASE REPORT)

Erdheim-Chester Disease with multisystem involvement: A diagnostic dilemma mimicking autoimmune and inflammatory diseases: Case report and a brief literature review

Jonathan Nguyen ², Sabrina Escobar ³, Marina Moussa ², Rujul Patel ³, Simran Agarwal ³, Katherine Castrichini ², Oliver Stewart ³, Jessica Jahoda ^{1,2} and Mohamed Aziz ^{1,4,*}

¹ Research Writing & Publication (RWP), LLC, NY, USA.

² American University of the Caribbean School of Medicine USA.

³ Ross University School of Medicine, Barbados.

⁴ Saint Vincent's Comprehensive Cancer Center, New York City, NY.

World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2025, 23(02), 001-009

Publication history: Received on 22 June 2025; revised on 29 July 2025; accepted on 01 August 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2025.23.2.0725>

Abstract

Erdheim-Chester Disease (ECD) is a rare, non-Langerhans cell histiocytosis involving xanthogranulomatous infiltration of various organ systems. It is difficult to diagnose because of its heterogeneous and nonspecific clinical presentation. This case report follows the tortuous diagnostic journey of a 55-year-old female with ECD, who initially presented with bone pain and bilateral exophthalmos, did not respond to early treatment and later developed cardiac, pulmonary, renal, and central nervous system symptoms.

In more than three years, several medical work-ups have been performed by several specialists with broad differential diagnoses that included autoimmune diseases, cancer and inflammatory or viral related diseases. Initial studies lacked consistency and were complicated by overlapping symptoms related to diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus, sarcoidosis, orbital lymphoma, and Grave's disease.

The diagnosis was determined following the lung biopsy results which showed characteristic histiocytes with CD68 positive, CD163 positive, CD1a negative, and lipid-laden histiocytes. These lung biopsy findings were corroborated by radiological manifestations of bilateral long bone osteosclerosis, pericardial disease, retroperitoneal fibrosis, and thickening of the pituitary stalk. Further investigations revealed the presence of a BRAF V600E mutation and this confirmed the diagnosis. The patient was then placed on Vemurafenib with impressive clinical response.

This case illustrates the protean nature of ECD, and the need to have a high index of suspicion in patients with unexplained multi-system disease. Rapid tissue diagnosis is not only of relevance to the molecular profiling and accuracy of the diagnosis, but also to direct personalized therapy. Thus, ECD should be considered in the differential diagnoses of other widespread disease that consider patients with non-specific osteoarticular pain and systemic symptoms that have not been sufficiently justified by clinical and radiographic results.

Keywords: Erdheim-Chester Disease; Inflammatory; Neoplastic; Histiocytes; Molecular; Immunohistochemistry

1. Introduction

ECD is a unique non-Langerhans cell histiocytosis that includes foam histiocyte-laden tissue infiltrates that are CD68 positive and CD1a negative. [1] In most cases, ECD presents as a typical pattern of autoimmune, neoplastic, and

* Corresponding author: Mohamed Aziz

inflammatory disorders, thereby complicating the diagnosis. ECD is traditionally seen during adulthood, in patients aged 40-70 years. Somatic mutations that activate MAPK pathway, especially the BRAF V600E mutation and the MAP2K1 gene, are linked to ECD. [1] It is noteworthy that early detection is crucial because BRAF selective targeting inhibitor, namely Vemurafenib, demonstrates a high clinical outcome. [2]

Clinically, ECD may manifest heterogeneously in patients from bone pains and retroperitoneal fibrosis to life threatening cardiovascular, renal, pulmonary, and central nervous system disease. The diagnostic process includes histopathologic identification of typical histiocytes in the involved tissue, immunohistochemistry (IHC) studies, and molecular testing of mutations in the MAPK pathway. [3] Imaging characteristics, including scintigraphic bilateral symmetric long bone uptake and characteristic radiologic findings, are very suggestive.

ECD treatment is based on the profile of the patient, the level of illness, and the type of mutations. Historically, first line treatment was Interferon- alpha. However, in cases where the patient manifested severe pain, multisystem involvement, or refractory disease, especially in patients with identified mutations, BRAF and MEK inhibitors are favored. [4] In select cases, there are other treatments that can be used such as anti-cytokine therapy and immunosuppression. [5]

In this report, we summarize the three-year diagnostic journey of a 55-year-old woman highlighting the challenges of diagnosing ECD. It required several specialist visits to diagnose her disease due to varying symptoms including fluctuating bilateral exophthalmos, refractory bone pains, cardiac, pulmonary, and endocrine failures. After the lung biopsy and molecular profiling that identified the underlying pathology, targeted therapy using a BRAF inhibitor was introduced with an exceptional clinical turnaround. We highlight the importance of integrating histologic, radiologic, and molecular findings in successfully identifying and treating this rare disease. We also point out the increased need of physician awareness of ECD to reduce the delays in diagnosing and treatment.

2. Case presentation

A 55-year-old female patient complained of a 3-year history of multisystemic progressive symptoms, which began with persistent, aching bilateral leg pain (more marked in the knees and ankles), and later, bilateral painless exophthalmos. The bony pain was intractable to conventional analgesics and was only transiently relieved by multiple courses of steroids. Additional clinical findings included a chronic dry cough and non-specific chest discomfort. She had no prior symptoms, no history of autoimmune or hematological disease, and no significant family history.

The ocular manifestations of the disease progressed and became bilateral exophthalmos, diplopia, decrease in visual acuity and the presence of the medial canthi yellowish plaques and firm orbital masses. The onset of the cardiac symptoms was insidious, and it was initially attributed to be stress-induced. She gradually became dyspneic upon exertion, her exercise capacity was diminished, with occasional chest pain. These findings led to an assessment attempting to rule out viral pericarditis, IgG4-related disease, and autoimmune diseases including systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) and even malignancy.

Laboratories, chest radiographs, and algorithms of clinical suspicion all contributed to the delay in the diagnosis of this patient. Her clinical picture of dry cough and discomfort led to her seeing multiple specialists of different disciplines in several areas. She subsequently developed symptoms of diabetes insipidus, such as polydipsia, polyuria, fatigue, and headache. At the same time, she became aware of yellowish xanthelasma type lesions on her eyelids. This expanded the differential diagnosis to be considered in line with Graves' disease, orbital lymphoma, and granulomatosis with polyangiitis. Given multifactorial presentation; more common autoimmune diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, SLE, polymyalgia rheumatica and sarcoidosis, were considered.

Laboratory tests showed non-specific elevations of inflammatory markers, and initial imaging was ambiguous, showing low-grade inflammatory alterations; As the patient's symptoms progressed, radiologic studies began to clarify the process. The X-rays revealed symmetrical diaphyseal sclerosis of the long bones, sparing the joints, and the Bone Scintigram (99mTc) revealed increased symmetrical uptake of the long bones at the level of the knees and the ankles. Metabolically active bone lesions were identified using the FDG-PET. Chest and abdominal CT showed lung interlobular septal thickening, ground-glass opacities, and abdominal retroperitoneal fibrosis, which was concerning for carcinomatosis. Cardiac CT and MRI showed thickening of the pericardium, and mass-like lesion in the right atrium. MRI of the brain and orbital region showed proptosis, thickened pituitary stalk, and enlarged extraocular muscles.

These findings raised suspicion for ECD. One of the specialists that the patient consulted during her diagnosing process ordered a lung biopsy, which led to the definitive diagnosis. The lung was sampled using video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS) to obtain the sampling of the tissue. Microscopic analysis revealed typical ECD features showing

macrophages with lipid laden and giant cells with multiple nuclei, in background of fibrosis. This fibrosis was seen in the interstitial spaces, pleura, and septa. The pattern of fibrosis resembled other interstitial lung diseases, like non-specific interstitial pneumonia or usual interstitial pneumonia; however, the foamy xanthomatous histiocytes were characteristic of ECD. (Figure 2 A, B, C) Histopathological differential diagnosis included reactive histiocytic proliferations, Langerhans cell histiocytosis, xanthogranuloma, and Rosai-Dorfman disease. IHC studies revealed the CD68 and CD163 positive macrophages and the CD1a negative ones, indicative of ECD and excluding Langerhans cell histiocytosis. S100 was also negative excluding Rosai-Dorfman disease. The confirmation of the diagnosis was done by the presence of the BRAF V600E mutation in molecular testing that was also useful therapeutically to administer treatment using anti BRAF targeted therapy.

There was multidisciplinary management. She was started on BRAF inhibitor, vemurafenib, and she had a good clinical and radiologic response. Bone pain was managed by bisphosphonates. Pericardiocentesis and steroids were given. The orbital lesions that threatened vision were treated using radiation in the form of low doses. Diabetes insipidus and electrolytes were treated with desmopressin. There was an improvement in lung lesions without any direct pulmonary treatment.

The patient was stable without significant complications and the symptoms were nearly resolved at about three years after the diagnosis and the best treatment had been established. She had the ability to resume her daily life activities and she was able to control her chronic illness with the help of a well-coordinated specialty approach. Table 1 summarizes the patient demographics and key clinical features and Table 2 list the differential diagnoses and exclusion rationale.

Table 1 Patient Demographics and Key Clinical Features

Feature	Patient's Presentation
Age at Diagnosis	55 years
Gender	Female
Duration of Symptoms before Diagnosis	3 years
Initial Presenting Symptoms	Persistent, aching bilateral leg pain (knees and ankles), bilateral painless exophthalmos
Evolving Symptoms	Cardiac (dyspnea on exertion, diminished exercise capacity, chest pain), pulmonary (chronic dry cough, non-specific chest discomfort), endocrine (diabetes insipidus: polydipsia, polyuria, fatigue, headache), ocular (diplopia, decreased visual acuity, medial canthi yellowish plaques, firm orbital masses), yellowish xanthelasma-type lesions on eyelids
Relevant Past Medical History	Previously well, no history of autoimmune or hematological disease, no significant medical family history

1A Low power view showing nodular infiltrate of lung parenchyma (H&E stain X20) 1B: Intermediate power view showing mixture of foamy histiocytes, and inflammatory cells (H&E stain X40); 1C: High power view showing foamy xanthomatous histiocytes admixed with inflammatory cells and multinucleated giant cells in background of collagenous stroma (H&E stain X60)

Figure 1 Histomorphology of Erdheim-Chester disease (ECD), lung biopsy

Table 2 Differential Diagnoses and Exclusion Rationale

Differential Diagnosis	Rationale for Consideration	Rationale for Exclusion/Distinction from ECD
Autoimmune Diseases	Overlapping symptoms (e.g., bone pain, exophthalmos, multisystemic involvement, inflammatory markers)	Lack of specific markers
Rheumatoid Arthritis	Nonspecific osteoarticular pain	Lack of specific RA markers, presence of other atypical symptoms
Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE)	Multisystemic affection, cardiac symptoms	Lack of specific SLE markers, atypical imaging findings
Sarcoidosis	Dry cough, non-specific chest discomfort, interlobular septal and pleural thickening, ground-glass opacities, retroperitoneal fibrosis on CT	Histopathology (absence of non-caseating granulomas), presence of specific ECD imaging features (e.g., long bone sclerosis, hairy kidney), positive BRAF V600E mutation
Graves' Disease	Bilateral exophthalmos, diplopia, decreased visual acuity	Presence of systemic symptoms beyond thyroid involvement, atypical orbital findings, lack of thyroid dysfunction
Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (GPA)	Multisystemic affection, ocular involvement	Lack of specific GPA markers (e.g., ANCA), atypical histopathology, presence of specific ECD features
IgG4-related disease	Cardiac symptoms, pericardial involvement, retroperitoneal fibrosis	Lack of elevated IgG4 levels, specific histopathological features of ECD
Neoplastic Diseases	Multisystemic involvement, mass-like lesions, progressive symptoms	Histopathology (absence of malignant cells), specific histiocytic infiltration
Orbital Lymphoma	Orbital masses, proptosis	Histopathology (absence of lymphoma cells), specific histiocytic infiltration
Lymphangitic Carcinomatosis	Pulmonary findings (interlobular septal and pleural thickening, ground-glass opacities)	Histopathology (absence of carcinoma cells), specific histiocytic infiltration

3. Discussion

3.1. History, epidemiology, and risk factors

ECD is a rare non-Langerhans cell histiocytosis, which was first presented by Jakob Erdheim and William Chester in 1930 under the name lipid granulomatosis. [8] In 2014, the first set of diagnosis and treatment recommendations of ECD was published. [5] ECD has been reclassified as a neoplastic disorder as opposed to chronic inflammatory disease and is currently included in the 2022 World Health Organization (WHO), 5th edition classification of hematopoietic and lymphoid neoplasms. [6]

It also belongs to the L (Langerhans) category in the updated 2016 histiocytosis classification of the Histiocyte Society. [7] The progress in the field of molecular biology, specifically the discovery of targetable mutations, including BRAF-V600E has had a major effect on how the disease is diagnosed and treated, resulting in the identification and approval of therapies like vemurafenib in the case of mutation-positive individuals. [5]

ECD is mostly detected in adults between the age of 40 and 70 years. [8] [9] The age range is however wider with cases reported as low as 7 years and as old as 84 years. [10] and although pediatric presentation is rare, it has been reported in the literature [8]

The disease shows a slight male predominance with diagnosis occurring later in life for men compared to women. [11] [12] ECD can initially present as a juvenile xanthogranulomatous lesion of the central nervous system in rare cases of the pediatric population and often presents with the BRAF-V600E mutation, with a higher occurrence in males. [5] Also, geographic clustering has been witnessed. A geoepidemiologic study in France and Italy showed that the prevalence is greater in certain areas, especially in southern Italy and central France, which is an indication of growing awareness as well as possible environmental or genetic factors [13].

ECD may manifest with various systemic symptoms, including but not limited to musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, neurologic, retroperitoneal, pulmonary, and endocrine involvement. These wide-ranging manifestations frequently contribute to diagnostic delays [14]. On imaging, the most characteristic skeletal feature is bilateral, symmetric sclerosis of the diaphyseal and metaphyseal regions, typically sparing the epiphyses [15]. These changes are most pronounced in the femur, tibia, and fibula. Radiographs may show cortical thickening alongside medullary sclerosis, sometimes creating a classic "bone-within-bone" appearance. [16] Retroperitoneal fibrosis ("hairy kidney" on imaging studies), and periaortic fibrosis ("coated aorta") occur in over half of ECD patients, making these important diagnostic clues. [14] [16]. On bone scintigraphy using technetium-99m, symmetric and intensely increased tracer uptake is observed in these regions, producing what is referred to as a "hot-on-hot" appearance due to combined cortical and medullary involvement. [14] MRI shows low T1 and heterogeneous T2 signals, with post-contrast enhancement reflecting inflammation and infiltration. MRI is vital for assessing marrow involvement and soft-tissue masses. [14]

CT imaging frequently shows bilateral, infiltrative soft-tissue masses in the perirenal or posterior pararenal spaces. These lesions are usually similar in density to skeletal muscle and demonstrate mild contrast enhancement. [1] On MRI, they tend to appear isointense or slightly hypointense relative to Skeletal muscle on T1- as well as T2-weighted sequences which slightly enhances with contrast administration. [15] A very characteristic example is the so-called hairy kidney sign, in which the perirenal fat is infiltrated by histiocytes to develop spiculated, irregular margins around the kidneys [14].

Cardiac involvement is another important characteristic of ECD, and it is usually associated with poor prognosis. [15] The disease may involve any of the cardiac structures; thickening of the pericardium and effusion are some of the most frequent manifestations, which may culminate into cardiac tamponade. Mass-like lesion, also known as the pseudotumor, may be observed in 40 percent of the cases due to infiltration of the right atrium or atrioventricular groove by the involved histiocytes and associated fibrosis. [17] Patchy delayed enhancement of the myocardium which is not consistent with normal coronary artery distribution may be seen on cardiac MRI. The other finding can include endocardial thickening, valvular diseases, and conduction system illness. [14]

For the pulmonary changes, the imaging mode of choice is the High-Resolution Computed Tomography (HRCT). Typical thoracic imaging is seen in the form of interlobular and intralobular septal thickening, ground-glass opacities, pleural effusion, and pleural thickening. There can be centrilobular and to a lesser extent large parenchymal nodules or masses. Even though these changes are mostly nonspecific, they might be clinically useful in support of a diagnosis when they are combined with systemic and skeletal findings. [14]

For central nervous system manifestations, MRI should be used to assess this condition. It may happen in the hypothalamic-pituitary region and is associated with central diabetes insipidus usually. Additional typical findings are dural-based masses, many of which may be similar to meningiomas, as well as parenchymal lesions within the brainstem or cerebellum, which is T2/FLAIR hyperintense, and frequently variably enhancing. [15]

3.2. Pathogenesis-pathophysiology

ECD can now be categorized as clonal hematopoietic disorder and neoplastic in nature. This categorization is further supported by the high occurrences of mutations in MAPK signaling pathways, including BRAF V600E in this patient group. [8] ECD is at least suspected to be a disease entity along the inflammatory/neoplastic spectrum just like classic hematologic malignancies by virtue of its discovery of origin in mutant progenitors, as recounted in recent literature. [18] Also known is that the mutations seen in ECD are frequently found in other myeloid neoplasms. [18] This combination of clinical and genetic similarities also confirms the clonal relationship between ECD and myeloid neoplasms.

The somatic mutations (mainly in BRAF, namely V600E) play a key role in the pathogenesis of the ECD and are reported in approximately 50-70% of the cases. [19] Apart from BRAF, mutations of other genes in the MAPK pathway, such as MAP2K1 (MEK1) have also been found in a few patients and highlight the relevance of this pathway in ECD. These activating mutations cause the continuous turning on of the MAPK/ERK pathway, a critical signaling pathway in cell

growth and proliferation as well as detection. [5] This abnormal signal is the cause of the abnormal proliferation of histiocytes and invasion to tissues that lead to the polymorphic clinical features of the disease. The presence of these mutations demonstrates ECD is not an inflammatory or an autoimmune disease, as previously thought, but a neoplastic disease.

Immunological, inflammatory, and genetic factors are implicated in the pathogenesis of ECD. [19] Systemic proinflammatory cytokines (including IFN- α , IL-12 and MCP-1/CCL2) were also detected in accumulating amounts in ECD. [20] This cytokine milieu induces the chemoattraction of and the chronic activation of the histiocytes. This induction causes the chronic cytokine stimulation and their persistent activation which will further perpetuate the inflammatory response causing tissue destruction and fibrosis. [20] There is a strong interrelation between the genetic MAPK pathway mutation phenotypes and the chronic inflammatory, mutagenic, and hormonal environment. [19] This interrelation fosters a complex pathogenic terrain, and one that moves from the creation of disease to its systemic symptomatologic expressions.

3.3. Molecular changes

ECD is currently considered a clonal myeloid neoplasm with reoccurring activating mutations, which mostly affect the MAPK (RAS-RAF-MEK-ERK) and PI3K-AKT pathways. These mutations have been found in a high number of ECD patients since 2012. [19] A 2015 whole-exome sequencing study interrogated 14 fresh-frozen ECD tissue specimens, and identified point mutations in genes, including ARAF, MAP2K1, NRAS, and PI3KCA. It was interesting to note that 14% of such cases showed novel MAP2K1 mutations and additional MAP2K1 mutations were also found in 50% of BRAF-wild-type ECD cases upon further validation. [5] Additional mutations are well-known activating mutations in KRAS and NRAS and PI3K pathway alteration, including mutations of PI3KCA. ARAF gene mutations were detected in 21 percent of samples and two samples were mutually exclusive of BRAF-V600E. Besides, gene fusions with ALK have also been described, indicating a wider genetic variability in the pathogenesis of ECD. [5]

3.4. Management and prognosis

ECD is a very rare multisystem disease with multiorgan involvement. The management and treatment of ECD should be individualized and molecular change centered. Proper molecular diagnosis, frequently with the assistance of a team of specialists, requires early detection prior to the enactment of the most appropriate treatment and monitoring procedures. Patients that have an activating mutation of the MAPK-ERK pathway and are symptomatic typically respond to targeted therapies against the activating mutation. They are either BRAF inhibitors (including Vemurafenib), MEK inhibitors (based on MEK protein, which is a component of the signaling pathway stimulating cell growth) or a combination. [1] In the present case, our patient, who was diagnosed with ECD with activating BRAF mutation, demonstrated a favorable response with Vemurafenib, which has been reported to have also beneficial effects in patients not carrying the BRAF mutation. [5] Vemurafenib has demonstrated stunning results in some clinical trials, such as a 2-year overall survival rate of 96% for the BRIM-3 trial and 86% progression-free survival for BRIM-1 as well as a 62% response rate. [5] [21] However, data support that patients with central nervous system (CNS) or other visceral organ involvement should also be considered for dual therapy, such as a BRAF inhibitor combined with an MEK inhibitor. While not necessarily shown in a head-to-head prospective manner in clinical trials, this dual therapy is more efficacious than monotherapy. [21] MEK inhibitors (e.g., Cobimetinib) and interferon-alpha have demonstrated some potential success for those without a BRAF mutation or who fail BRAF inhibitors. [1]

It is necessary to maintain long-term surveillance for prevention of disease progression, control of therapy-based side effects and avoidance of possible complications. Corticosteroids, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy are other possible therapeutic options, usually only employed in palliative and symptomatic situations. [5] It should be reminded that radiation therapy is not curative, as ECD is not a radiosensitive disease. [5] Asymptomatic patients without CNS involvement or other significant organ dysfunction may undergo a period of observation rather than immediate treatment. [21]

ECD prognosis depends on the location of the disease, the response to treatment and, most importantly, the central nervous system involvement. Amongst the factors that led to a less favorable prognosis are advanced age and disease of the CNS, lungs, and retroperitoneum. [1] CNS involvement is a powerful and independent factor of mortality. [5] Pulmonary system involvement has been also recognized as an independent predictor of poor prognosis by means of multivariate analysis. [1].

3.5. What does the future hold for the diagnosis and treatment of ECD? and what did we learn from this case?

The dramatic change that is about to be experienced in the ECD diagnostic and therapeutic terrain is mostly attributed to revolutions in technology. Precision medicine will improve, and more complex, genomic sequencing beyond BRAF V600E, to define a variety of MAPK pathway mutations and additional genetic drivers is expected. [4] This will enable early and proper diagnoses even in cases with atypical presentations. Imaging results will also undergo change due to improved PET/CT and magnetic resonance (MR) technologies which potentially coincide with the use of artificial intelligence (AI) to analyze images and improve the detection of lesions and characterization of disease. [22] A less invasive alternative, liquid biopsies, can be used to monitor the disease process and response to treatment through circulating biomarkers. [Reference] The most probable changes in treatment will involve an increased focus on targeted therapies, next generation drugs BRAF and MEK inhibitors, and more efficacy with a reduced toxicity profile. Here, the immunotherapies combined with targeted therapies may be a new promising therapy mode. [23] Additionally, machine learning and AI will play a role in personalization of a treatment plan, optimizing the treatment algorithm to a patient. International registries and collaboration are also important to acquire enough data to inform future research and clinical practice in this rare disease.

A case presentation is of great importance in the context of a rare disease such as ECD. They are useful in clinical description of unusual or novel clinical presentations, responses to treatment or diagnostic findings which are not recorded in larger clinical trials. A case report may introduce controversial symptoms and involvement or reactions of body or organs to treat that do not correspond to existing paradigms and thereby may be the origin of additional research hypotheses. Moreover, it leads to strengthening the awareness of clinician, which can help make the earlier diagnosis and a favorable prognosis of a patient. [24] [25]

4. Conclusion

Increased awareness of Erdheim-Chester Disease's (ECD) protean manifestations is essential to reduce diagnostic delays and improve patient outcomes. This case report demonstrates the diagnostic challenges related to ECD, a rare systemic histiocytosis with a tendency to have an indistinct clinical presentation. The odyssey of this 3-year diagnostic journey for our patient from specialist to specialist is a telling story of how ECD can be a challenging diagnosis. It is important to keep ECD on the list of differentials when it comes to a patient presenting with a triad of bone pain, exophthalmos, and multifocal systemic involvement. The radiologic findings of bilateral diaphyseal sclerosis sparing of the joints, findings that are discriminatory and that were supported by tissue biopsy which revealed CD68+/CD163+/CD11a- macrophages were used to confirm the diagnosis. The presence of BRAF V600E mutation was identified, confirming the diagnosis; Targeted therapy was provided in the form of Vemurafenib that resulted in outstanding clinical response. In this case, the critical nature of multidisciplinary approach in the diagnosis and treatment of ECD is evident. This approach included molecular therapy, supportive care, and organ-based interventions. Possible early detection of this potentially fatal disease and early treatment can make it of good prognosis, thus making it necessary to create awareness about this illness among all clinicians.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Special thanks to MD candidates Maryam Naeem, Tori Richmond, and Logan Bemby for their assistance in reviewing the final manuscript.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The following declarations are made by all authors:

- **Payment/services information:** All authors have declared that they received no financial support from any organization for the submitted work.
- **Financial relationships:** All authors have declared that they have no financial relationships at present or within the previous three years with any organizations that might be interested in the submitted work.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical review and approval were not required for this study involving human participants. The paper has been sufficiently anonymized to maintain the patient's confidentiality.

Data access statement

All relevant data are included in the paper.

Author contributions

All authors contributed equally to producing this manuscript.

Statement of informed consent

The patient was lost to follow-up, and all attempts to reach the family members were unsuccessful. Therefore, the paper has been sufficiently anonymized to maintain patient confidentiality.

References

- [1] Haroche J, Cohen-Aubart F, Amoura Z. Erdheim-Chester disease. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology*. 2020 Apr 16;135(16):1311-8.
- [2] Campochiaro C, Tomelleri A, Cavalli G, Berti A, Dagna L. Erdheim-Chester disease. *European journal of internal medicine*. 2015 May 1;26(4):223-9.
- [3] Ozkaya N, Rosenblum MK, Durham BH, Pichardo JD, Abdel-Wahab O, Hameed MR, Busam KJ, Travis WD, Diamond EL, Dogan A. The histopathology of Erdheim-Chester disease: a comprehensive review of a molecularly characterized cohort. *Modern Pathology*. 2018 Apr 1;31(4):581-97.
- [4] Kulkarni AM, Gayam PK, Aranjan JM. Advances in understanding and management of Erdheim-Chester disease. *Life Sciences*. 2024 Jul 1;348:122692.
- [5] Goyal G, Heaney ML, Collin M, Cohen-Aubart F, Vaglio A, Durham BH, Hershkovitz-Rokah O, Girschikofsky M, Jacobsen ED, Toyama K, Goodman AM. Erdheim-Chester disease: consensus recommendations for evaluation, diagnosis, and treatment in the molecular era. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology*. 2020 May 28;135(22):1929-45.
- [6] Li W. The 5th edition of the World Health Organization classification of hematolymphoid tumors. *Exon Publications*. 2022 Oct 16:1-21.
- [7] Emile JF, Ablu O, Fraitag S, Horne A, Haroche J, Donadieu J, Requena-Caballero L, Jordan MB, Abdel-Wahab O, Allen CE, Charlotte F. Revised classification of histiocytoses and neoplasms of the macrophage-dendritic cell lineages. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology*. 2016 Jun 2;127(22):2672-81.
- [8] Mazor RD, Manevich-Mazor M, Shoenfeld Y. Erdheim-Chester Disease: a comprehensive review of the literature. *Orphanet Journal of rare diseases*. 2013 Sep 8;8(1):137.
- [9] Volpicelli ER, Doyle L, Annes JP, Murray MF, Jacobsen E, Murphy GF, Saavedra AP. Erdheim-Chester disease presenting with cutaneous involvement: a case report and literature review. *Journal of cutaneous pathology*. 2011 Mar;38(3):280-5.
- [10] Veyssier-Belot C, Cacoub P, Caparros-Lefebvre D, Wechsler J, Brun B, Remy M, Wallaert B, Petit H, Grimaldi A, Wechsler B, Godeau P. Erdheim-Chester disease clinical and radiologic characteristics of 59 cases. *Medicine*. 1996 May 1;75(3):157-69.
- [11] Drier A, Haroche J, Savatovsky J, Godenèche G, Dormont D, Chiras J, Amoura Z, Bonneville F. Cerebral, facial, and orbital involvement in Erdheim-Chester disease: CT and MR imaging findings. *Radiology*. 2010 May;255(2):586-94.
- [12] Allen TC, Chevez-Barrios P, Shetlar DJ, Cagle PT: Pulmonary and ophthalmic involvement with Erdheim-Chester disease: a case report and review of the literature. *Arch Pathol Lab Med*. 2004, 128: 1428-1431.
- [13] Peyronel F, Haroche J, Campochiaro C, Pegoraro F, Amoura Z, Tomelleri A, Mazzariol M, Papo M, Cavalli G, Benigno GD, Fenaroli P. Epidemiology and geographic clustering of Erdheim-Chester disease in Italy and France. *Blood*. 2023 Dec 14;142(24):2119-23.

- [14] de Oliveira Santo ID, Lerner G, Rubinowitz AN, Fadel SA, Chen MK, Mojibian HR, Mathur M. Decoding Erdheim-Chester Disease: a Pictorial Essay of the Radiologic and Pathologic Findings, and its Main Differential Diagnoses. *Clinical Radiology*. 2025 Jun 1;85.
- [15] Aswani Y, Patel A, Zhan X, Ansari S, Marcelino LG, Aswani N, Patel DD, Kandemirli S, Averill S, Bhatt S. Imaging in Erdheim-Chester disease. *RadioGraphics*. 2024 Aug 22;44(9):e240011.
- [16] Choraria A, Andrei V, Rajakulasingam R, Saifuddin A. Musculoskeletal imaging features of non-Langerhans cell histiocytoses. *Skeletal Radiology*. 2021 Oct;50(10):1921-40.
- [17] Gianfreda, D., Palumbo, A. A., Rossi, E., Buttarelli, L., Manari, G., Martini, C., De Filippo, M., & Vaglio, A. (2016). Cardiac involvement in Erdheim-Chester Disease: An MRI study. *Blood*, 128(20), 2468–2471. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2016-07-724815>
- [18] Eric Jacobsen MD, Gaurav Goyal, MD. Erdheim-Chester disease. UpToDate. (Accessed July 16, 2025). <https://www.uptodate.com/contents/erdheim-chester-disease>
- [19] Wilcox SR, Reynolds SB, Ahmed AZ. Erdheim-Chester Disease: Investigating the Correlation between Targeted Treatment Therapy and Disease Outcomes. *Cancers*. 2024 Mar 27;16(7):1299.
- [20] Cavalli G, Dagna L, Biavasco R, Villa A, Doglioni C, Ferrero E, Ferrarini M. Erdheim-Chester disease: An in vivo human model of M ϕ activation at the crossroad between chronic inflammation and cancer. *Journal of Leucocyte Biology*. 2020 Aug;108(2):591-9.
- [21] Abdelfattah AM, Arnaout K, Tabbara IA. Erdheim-Chester disease: a comprehensive review. *Anticancer research*. 2014 Jul 1;34(7):3257-61.
- [22] Chaudhary R, Kumar A, Singh A, Agarwal V, Rehman M, Kaushik AS, Srivastava S, Srivastava S, Mishra V. Erdheim-Chester disease: Comprehensive insights from genetic mutations to clinical manifestations and therapeutic advances. *Disease-a-Month*. 2025 Jan 4:101845.
- [23] Oiseth SJ, Aziz MS. Cancer immunotherapy: a brief review of the history, possibilities, and challenges ahead. *Journal of cancer metastasis and treatment*. 2017 Oct 31;3:250-61.
- [24] Poling MI, Dufresne CR. Strategies for Improving Case Reports Involving Patients With Rare Diseases. *Cureus*. 2025 Feb 28;17(2).
- [25] Sampayo-Cordero M, Miguel-Huguet B, Malfettone A, Pérez-García JM, Llombart-Cussac A, Cortés J, Pardo A, Pérez-López J. The value of case reports in systematic reviews from rare diseases. The example of enzyme replacement therapy (ERT) in patients with mucopolysaccharidosis type II (MPS-II). *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2020 Sep;17(18):6590.